

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: [Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences](#)

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 130

Issue Regularity: [Monthly](#)

Review Process: [Double Blind](#)

Time to Publication: 21 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

● **DOI:** 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: [iThenticate](#)

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

License: Open Access by Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. Based on a work at SciRes Literature LLC.

Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

**IndexCopernicus
ICV 2020:
53.77**

 Vision: Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences main aim is to enhance the importance of science and technology to the scientific community and also to provide an equal opportunity to seek and share ideas to all our researchers and scientists without any barriers to develop their career and helping in their development of discovering the world.

MINI REVIEW

COVID-19 and Stress Response

Shaoqing Lai*

National Cancer Center/National Clinical Research Center for Cancer/Cancer Hospital, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences and Peking Union Medical College, Beijing, 100021, China

ABSTRACT

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 has become a global public health emergency. The novel coronavirus is becoming more contagious through continuous evolution, it is difficult to prevent transmission. The patients of COVID-19 suffer from severe pneumonia and complex systemic manifestations. Reducing the damage of COVID-19 to the human body becomes particularly important. In this review, we reviewed the similarity and particularity of viral infectious diseases to understand the pathogenic mechanisms of COVID-19 and to explore optimal therapy for COVID-19.

INTRODUCTION

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) has become a global public health emergency with many unprecedented challenges as well as important economic, political, and epidemiological implications [1–6]. The novel coronavirus is becoming more and more contagious through continuous evolution, it is difficult to prevent transmission of COVID-19. The patients of COVID-19 suffer from severe pneumonia and complex systemic manifestations [7–14], particularly in those with comorbidities [10–16]. It becomes particularly important to reduce the damage of COVID-19 to the human body. To evaluate current therapy and to find future optimal therapy for COVID-19, the pathogenic mechanisms of viral infectious disease must be understood, as optimal therapy should be directed primarily against these pathogenic mechanisms. Therefore, we reviewed the similarity and particularity of viral infectious diseases to understand the pathogenic mechanisms of COVID-19 and to explore optimal therapy for COVID-19.

Similarity and particularity of viral infectious diseases

Viruses have no vitality *in vitro*; they only replicate in living cells. Viruses have a specific tissue affinity, different viruses choose different tissue cells to replicate, such as mumps virus replicates in parotid cells, hepatitis virus replicates in liver cells, influenza virus replicates in upper airway cells, and novel coronavirus replicates in alveolar cells.

The viral infection triggers organism immune response to the viruses. Immune cells synthesize antibodies of virus through genetic recombination to capture free virus and destroy the cells virus replicated in leading to cell necrosis and local inflammation. The tissue affinity of viruses results in proprietary symptoms of different viral infection. If the organism immune cells cannot synthesize antibodies of the virus through genetic recombination allowing the virus to replicate, the people become asymptomatic and healthy carriers of the virus.

The viral infection also induces organism stress response meanwhile. The stress response coordinates the functions of various systems of organism to ensure that the body is able to survive dangerous period. In stress response, the locus

*Corresponding author

Shaoqing Lai, National Cancer Center/
National Clinical Research Center for
Cancer/Cancer Hospital, Chinese Academy
of Medical Sciences and Peking Union
Medical College, Beijing, 100021, China

Tel: +86-10-13683213875

ORCID: 0000-0001-5809-0481

E-mail: 13683213875@163.com; shaoqing-lai@cicams.ac.cn

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1479

Submitted: 05 May 2022

Accepted: 18 May 2022

Published: 18 May 2022

Copyright: © 2022 Lai S. Distributed under
Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

Keywords

- Coronavirus
- Pathogenesis
- COVID-19
- Stress response
- Therapy
- Healthy carriers

MEDICINE GROUP

EPIDEMIOLOGY

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 5 - MAY, 2022

coeruleus sympathetic adrenal medulla system is excited firstly, followed by the excitation of the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal cortex axis. Stress response can mobilize and integrate body functions, and inhibit the excessive inflammatory response. When intense stress response exceeds potential of endocrine, endocrine is exhausted. Patients with well potential of endocrine are mild and recover quickly. Patients with poor potential of endocrine are severe and recover slowly. Endocrine failure results in deterioration of the disease, inflammatory storms and multiple system organ failure. Nonspecific symptoms of viral infectious diseases, such as fever, headache, diarrhea, fatigue, etc., are manifestations of disorder and failure of endocrine.

Manifestations of COVID-19

COVID-19 is acute respiratory syndrome spanned from a mild influenza-like illness to life-threatening complications [17-19]. The novel coronavirus uses the ACE2 receptor to facilitate viral entry into the target cells to replicate. Approximately 83% of the ACE2 receptors are expressed on the luminal surface of alveolar epithelial type II cells, other ACE2 receptors are distributed in extra-pulmonary tissues, including heart, kidney, endothelium, and intestine. The viral invasion initiates immune response to destroy the cells that contain viral particles and lead to lung inflammation. Additionally, the multi-organ dysfunction observed in these patients can be attributed to the wide distribution of ACE2 receptors in extra-pulmonary tissues [20]. The pro-inflammatory cytokines released by the CD4 T-cells and cytotoxic granules in CD8 T-cells contributed to the severe immune injury in the patient. Diffuse alveolar immune damage with cellular fibromyxoid exudates and pulmonary edema, desquamation of pneumocytes, lymphocytes infiltration and hyaline membrane formation led to Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS) [21]. The sequelae of pulmonary fibrosis and dyspnea due to lung immune damage.

Older age group (65 years old) is at higher risk of developing severe infection because of higher proportion of established co-morbidities [22]. Children are less prone to develop symptomatic infection and severe disease [23].

The common nonspecific complaints of COVID-19 are fever, cough, and dyspnea, and less frequently gastrointestinal symptoms like diarrhea [24,25]. Furthermore, there are many phenomena not related to inflammation in the lungs occurred during the course of COVID-19, such as, taste alterations and olfactory disturbances, cutaneous manifestations such as erythematous rashes and urticaria, neurological manifestations such as headache, altered conscious state, and dizziness, etc. [26-28]. COVID-19 also associated with the involvement of the cardiovascular cerebrovascular system and autoimmune diseases [28-32]. Patients of COVID-19 usually have sequelae of taste alterations, loss of appetite, weakness and fatigue for a long

time after recovery. Those manifestations are difficult to explain in terms of pneumonia. Those manifestations are the result of disorder and failure of endocrine.

Myths and difficulties in the prevention and treatment of COVID-19

The original host of the novel coronavirus is still unclear. Whether the novel coronavirus can coexist with humans depends on whether there are healthy virus carriers in the crowd. There are a large number of asymptomatic carriers in COVID-19 pandemic [33]. The asymptomatic carriers are different from healthy carriers. The asymptomatic carriers should be defined as patients that there are immune responses to the virus in the body but no clinical symptoms, and the healthy carriers should be defined as healthy persons that the virus is replicated continually in the cells but no immune responses to the virus in the body. So far, there are no studies to confirm the existence of healthy carriers of novel coronavirus.

Stress response plays an important role in prognosis of COVID-19. The current therapies of COVID-19 are mainly antiviral therapy and adjuvant supportive care [34]. There are less therapies for the stress response in course of COVID-19. Evidences shown that low dose dexamethasone can reduce the death rate by one-third for patients of COVID-19 who require ventilation [35], and timing of the steroid therapy will prevent ARDS [34]. World Health Organization (WHO) now strongly recommends systemic corticosteroids for the treatment of patients with severe and critical COVID-19 based on moderate certainty evidence.

Traditional Chinese medicine is a medical system different from western medicine. Western medicine treats diseases the pathogen. Traditional Chinese medicine treats diseases according to stress responses. The drug target of traditional Chinese medicine in the treatment of viral diseases is to calm the excessive stress response and maintain the endocrine function. Appropriate use of traditional Chinese medicine will reduce the severe case and death rate, and help patients to recover from sequelae.

CONCLUSION

Viruses only replicate in living cells. The different viruses choose different tissue cells to replicate. Virus infection triggers immune response and stress response. Immune cells synthesize antibodies of virus to capture free virus and destroy the cells the virus replicate in leading to cell necrosis and inflammation. The stress response coordinates the functions of various systems of organism to ensure that the body survives the critical period. Intense stress response depletes the potential of endocrine resulting in deterioration of the disease, inflammatory storms and multiple system organ failure. Coexistence of viruses and humans depends on whether there are healthy virus carriers in the crowd.

The novel coronavirus uses the ACE2 receptor to facilitate viral entry into alveolar cells to replicate. Immune cells produce antibodies to capture free virus and destroy the cells the virus replicate in leading to a respiratory tract disease ranged from mild to severe. Patients with well potential of endocrine are mild and recover quickly. Patients with poor potential of endocrine are severe and recover slowly.

REFEFENCES

- Paules CI, Marston HD, Fauci AS. Coronavirus Infections-More Than Just the Common Cold. *JAMA*. 2020 Feb 25;323(8):707-708. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.0757. PMID: 31971553.
- Del Rio C, Malani PN. COVID-19-New Insights on a Rapidly Changing Epidemic. *JAMA*. 2020 Apr 14;323(14):1339-1340. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.3072. PMID: 32108857.
- Fauci AS, Lane HC, Redfield RR. Covid-19 - Navigating the Uncharted. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Mar 26;382(13):1268-1269. doi: 10.1056/NEJMe2002387. Epub 2020 Feb 28. PMID: 32109011; PMCID: PMC7121221.
- Ratzan SC, Gostin LO, Meshkati N, Rabin K, Parker RM. COVID-19: An Urgent Call for Coordinated, Trusted Sources to Tell Everyone What They Need to Know and Do. *NAM Perspect*. 2020 Mar 5;2020:10.31478/202003a. doi: 10.31478/202003a. PMID: 34532681; PMCID: PMC8406579.
- Gates B. Responding to Covid-19 - A Once-in-a-Century Pandemic? *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Apr 30;382(18):1677-1679. doi: 10.1056/NEJMp2003762. Epub 2020 Feb 28. PMID: 32109012.
- Alemanno A. Taming COVID-19 by regulation: an opportunity for self-reflection. *Eur J Risk Regul*. 2020;43(1):1-8. doi: 10.1017/err.2020.43.
- Guan WJ, Ni ZY, Hu Y, Liang WH, Ou CQ, He JX, Liu L, Shan H, Lei CL, Hui DSC, Du B, Li LJ, Zeng G, Yuen KY, Chen RC, Tang CL, Wang T, Chen PY, Xiang J, Li SY, Wang JL, Liang ZJ, Peng YX, Wei L, Liu Y, Hu YH, Peng P, Wang JM, Liu JY, Chen Z, Li G, Zheng ZJ, Qiu SQ, Luo J, Ye CJ, Zhu SY, Zhong NS; China Medical Treatment Expert Group for Covid-19. Clinical Characteristics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 in China. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Apr 30;382(18):1708-1720. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2002032. Epub 2020 Feb 28. PMID: 32109013; PMCID: PMC7092819.
- Xie J, Tong Z, Guan X, Du B, Qiu H. Clinical Characteristics of Patients Who Died of Coronavirus Disease 2019 in China. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2020 Apr 1;3(4):e205619. doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.5619. Erratum in: *JAMA Netw Open*. 2020 May 1;3(5):e208147. PMID: 32275319; PMCID: PMC7148440.
- Goyal P, Choi JJ, Pinheiro LC, Schenck EJ, Chen R, Jabri A, Satlin MJ, Campion TR Jr, Nahid M, Ringel JB, Hoffman KL, Alshak MN, Li HA, Wehmeyer GT, Rajan M, Reshetnyak E, Hupert N, Horn EM, Martinez FJ, Gulick RM, Safford MM. Clinical Characteristics of Covid-19 in New York City. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Jun 11;382(24):2372-2374. doi: 10.1056/NEJMc2010419. Epub 2020 Apr 17. PMID: 32302078; PMCID: PMC7182018.
- Richardson S, Hirsch JS, Narasimhan M, Crawford JM, McGinn T, Davidson KW; the Northwell COVID-19 Research Consortium, Barnaby DP, Becker LB, Chelico JD, Cohen SL, Cookingham J, Coppa K, Diefenbach MA, Dominello AJ, Duer-Hefele J, Falzon L, Gitlin J, Hajjzadeh N, Harvin TG, Hirschwerk DA, Kim EJ, Kozel ZM, Marrast LM, Mogavero JN, Osorio GA, Qiu M, Zanos TP. Presenting Characteristics, Comorbidities, and Outcomes Among 5700 Patients Hospitalized With COVID-19 in the New York City Area. *JAMA*. 2020 May 26;323(20):2052-2059. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.6775. Erratum in: *JAMA*. 2020 May 26;323(20):2098. PMID: 32320003; PMCID: PMC7177629.
- Cummings MJ, Baldwin MR, Abrams D, Jacobson SD, Meyer BJ, Balough EM, Aaron JG, Claassen J, Rabbani LE, Hastie J, Hochman BR, Salazar-Schicchi J, Yip NH, Brodie D, O'Donnell MR. Epidemiology, clinical course, and outcomes of critically ill adults with COVID-19 in New York City: a prospective cohort study. *Lancet*. 2020 Jun 6;395(10239):1763-1770. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)31189-2. Epub 2020 May 19. PMID: 32442528; PMCID: PMC7237188.
- Jutzeler CR, Bourguignon L, Weis CV, Tong B, Wong C, Rieck B, Pargger H, Tschudin-Sutter S, Egli A, Borgwardt K, Walter M. Comorbidities, clinical signs and symptoms, laboratory findings, imaging features, treatment strategies, and outcomes in adult and pediatric patients with COVID-19: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Travel Med Infect Dis*. 2020 Sep-Oct;37:101825. doi: 10.1016/j.tmaid.2020.101825. Epub 2020 Aug 4. PMID: 32763496; PMCID: PMC7402237.
- Guan WJ, Liang WH, Zhao Y, Liang HR, Chen ZS, Li YM, Liu XQ, Chen RC, Tang CL, Wang T, Ou CQ, Li L, Chen PY, Sang L, Wang W, Li JF, Li CC, Ou LM, Cheng B, Xiong S, Ni ZY,

- Xiang J, Hu Y, Liu L, Shan H, Lei CL, Peng YX, Wei L, Liu Y, Hu YH, Peng P, Wang JM, Liu JY, Chen Z, Li G, Zheng ZJ, Qiu SQ, Luo J, Ye CJ, Zhu SY, Cheng LL, Ye F, Li SY, Zheng JP, Zhang NF, Zhong NS, He JX; China Medical Treatment Expert Group for COVID-19. Comorbidity and its impact on 1590 patients with COVID-19 in China: a nationwide analysis. *Eur Respir J*. 2020 May 14;55(5):2000547. doi: 10.1183/13993003.00547-2020. PMID: 32217650; PMCID: PMC7098485.
- Wang T, Du Z, Zhu F, Cao Z, An Y, Gao Y, Jiang B. Comorbidities and multi-organ injuries in the treatment of COVID-19. *Lancet*. 2020 Mar 21;395(10228):e52. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30558-4. Epub 2020 Mar 11. PMID: 32171074; PMCID: PMC7270177.
- Yang J, Zheng Y, Gou X, Pu K, Chen Z, Guo Q, Ji R, Wang H, Wang Y, Zhou Y. Prevalence of comorbidities and its effects in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Infect Dis*. 2020 May;94:91-95. doi: 10.1016/j.ijid.2020.03.017. Epub 2020 Mar 12. PMID: 32173574; PMCID: PMC7194638.
- Sanyaolu A, Okorie C, Marinkovic A, Patidar R, Younis K, Desai P, Hosen Z, Padda I, Mangat J, Altaf M. Comorbidity and its Impact on Patients with COVID-19. *SN Compr Clin Med*. 2020;2(8):1069-1076. doi: 10.1007/s42399-020-00363-4. Epub 2020 Jun 25. PMID: 32838147; PMCID: PMC7314621.
- Jamil S, Mark N, Carlos G, Cruz CSD, Gross JE, Pasnick S. Diagnosis and Management of COVID-19 Disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2020 May 15;201(10):P19-P20. doi: 10.1164/rccm.2020C1. PMID: 32223716.
- Guan WJ, Ni ZY, Hu Y, Liang WH, Ou CQ, He JX, Liu L, Shan H, Lei CL, Hui DSC, Du B, Li LJ, Zeng G, Yuen KY, Chen RC, Tang CL, Wang T, Chen PY, Xiang J, Li SY, Wang JL, Liang ZJ, Peng YX, Wei L, Liu Y, Hu YH, Peng P, Wang JM, Liu JY, Chen Z, Li G, Zheng ZJ, Qiu SQ, Luo J, Ye CJ, Zhu SY, Zhong NS; China Medical Treatment Expert Group for Covid-19. Clinical Characteristics of Coronavirus Disease 2019 in China. *N Engl J Med*. 2020 Apr 30;382(18):1708-1720. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2002032. Epub 2020 Feb 28. PMID: 32109013; PMCID: PMC7092819.
- He X, Lau EHY, Wu P, Deng X, Wang J, Hao X, Lau YC, Wong JY, Guan Y, Tan X, Mo X, Chen Y, Liao B, Chen W, Hu F, Zhang Q, Zhong M, Wu Y, Zhao L, Zhang F, Cowling BJ, Li F, Leung GM. Temporal dynamics in viral shedding and transmissibility of COVID-19. *Nat Med*. 2020 May;26(5):672-675. doi: 10.1038/s41591-020-0869-5. Epub 2020 Apr 15. Erratum in: *Nat Med*. 2020 Sep;26(9):1491-1493. PMID: 32296168.
- Zhang H, Penninger JM, Li Y, Zhong N, Slutsky AS. Angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) as a SARS-CoV-2 receptor: molecular mechanisms and potential therapeutic target. *Intensive Care Med*. 2020 Apr;46(4):586-590. doi: 10.1007/s00134-020-05985-9. Epub 2020 Mar 3. PMID: 32125455; PMCID: PMC7098799.
- Li H, Liu L, Zhang D, Xu J, Dai H, Tang N, Su X, Cao B. SARS-CoV-2 and viral sepsis: observations and hypotheses. *Lancet*. 2020 May 9;395(10235):1517-1520. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30920-X. Epub 2020 Apr 17. PMID: 32311318; PMCID: PMC7164875.
- Ye ZW, Yuan S, Yuen KS, Fung SY, Chan CP, Jin DY. Zoonotic origins of human coronaviruses. *Int J Biol Sci*. 2020 Mar 15;16(10):1686-1697. doi: 10.7150/ijbs.45472. PMID: 32226286; PMCID: PMC7098031.
- Ludvigsson JF. Systematic review of COVID-19 in children shows milder cases and a better prognosis than adults. *Acta Paediatr*. 2020 Jun;109(6):1088-1095. doi: 10.1111/apa.15270. Epub 2020 Apr 14. PMID: 32202343; PMCID: PMC7228328.
- Zhang JJ, Dong X, Cao YY, Yuan YD, Yang YB, Yan YQ, Akdis CA, Gao YD. Clinical characteristics of 140 patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 in Wuhan, China. *Allergy*. 2020 Jul;75(7):1730-1741. doi: 10.1111/all.14238. Epub 2020 Feb 27. PMID: 32077115.
- Giacomelli A, Pezzati L, Conti F, Bernacchia D, Siano M, Oreni L, Rusconi S, Gervasoni C, Ridolfo AL, Rizzardini G, Antinori S, Galli M. Self-reported Olfactory and Taste Disorders in Patients With Severe Acute Respiratory Coronavirus 2 Infection: A Cross-sectional Study. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020 Jul 28;71(15):889-890. doi: 10.1093/cid/cia330. PMID: 32215618; PMCID: PMC7184514.
- Recalcati S. Cutaneous manifestations in COVID-19: a first perspective. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2020 May;34(5):e212-e213. doi: 10.1111/jdv.16387. PMID: 32215952.
- Mao L, Jin H, Wang M, Hu Y, Chen S, He Q, Chang J, Hong C, Zhou Y, Wang D, Miao X, Li Y, Hu B. Neurologic Manifestations of Hospitalized Patients With Coronavirus Disease 2019 in Wuhan, China. *JAMA Neurol*. 2020 Jun 1;77(6):683-690. doi: 10.1001/jamaneurol.2020.1127. PMID: 32275288; PMCID: PMC7149362.
- Wang D, Hu B, Hu C, Zhu F, Liu X, Zhang J, Wang B, Xiang H, Cheng Z, Xiong Y, Zhao Y, Li Y, Wang X, Peng Z. Clinical Characteristics of 138 Hospitalized Patients With

- 2019 Novel Coronavirus-Infected Pneumonia in Wuhan, China. *JAMA*. 2020 Mar 17;323(11):1061-1069. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.1585. Erratum in: *JAMA*. 2021 Mar 16;325(11):1113. PMID: 32031570; PMCID: PMC7042881.
29. Zheng YY, Ma YT, Zhang JY, Xie X. COVID-19 and the cardiovascular system. *Nat Rev Cardiol*. 2020 May;17(5):259-260. doi: 10.1038/s41569-020-0360-5. PMID: 32139904; PMCID: PMC7095524.
30. Long B, Brady WJ, Koyfman A, Gottlieb M. Cardiovascular complications in COVID-19. *Am J Emerg Med*. 2020 Jul;38(7):1504-1507. doi: 10.1016/j.ajem.2020.04.048. Epub 2020 Apr 18. PMID: 32317203; PMCID: PMC7165109.
31. Gracia-Ramos AE, Martin-Nares E, Hernández-Molina G. New Onset of Autoimmune Diseases Following COVID-19 Diagnosis. *Cells*. 2021 Dec 20;10(12):3592. doi: 10.3390/cells10123592. PMID: 34944099; PMCID: PMC8700122.
32. Gao WJ, Li LM. [Advances on presymptomatic or asymptomatic carrier transmission of COVID-19]. *Zhonghua Liu Xing Bing Xue Za Zhi*. 2020 Apr 10;41(4):485-488. Chinese. doi: 10.3760/cma.j.cn112338-20200228-00207. PMID: 32141279.
33. Stratton CW, Tang YW, Lu H. Pathogenesis-directed therapy of 2019 novel coronavirus disease. *J Med Virol*. 2021 Mar;93(3):1320-1342. doi: 10.1002/jmv.26610. Epub 2020 Nov 10. PMID: 33073355.
34. Mahase E. Covid-19: Low dose steroid cuts death in ventilated patients by one third, trial finds. *BMJ*. 2020 Jun 16;369:m2422. doi: 10.1136/bmj.m2422. PMID: 32546467.
35. RECOVERY Collaborative Group, Horby P, Lim WS, Emberson JR, Mafham M, Bell JL, Linsell L, Staplin N, Brightling C, Ustianowski A, Elmahi E, Prudon B, Green C, Felton T, Chadwick D, Rege K, Fegan C, Chappell LC, Faust SN, Jaki T, Jeffery K, Montgomery A, Rowan K, Juszczak E, Baillie JK, Haynes R, Landray MJ. Dexamethasone in Hospitalized Patients with Covid-19. *N Engl J Med*. 2021 Feb 25;384(8):693-704. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2021436. Epub 2020 Jul 17. PMID: 32678530; PMCID: PMC7383595.

How to cite this article: Lai S. COVID-19 and Stress Response. *J Biomed Res Environ Sci*. 2022 May 18; 3(5): 556-559. doi: 10.37871/jbres1479, Article ID: JBRES1479, Available at: <https://www.jelsciences.com/articles/jbres1479.pdf>